

SURE
SUSTAINABLE
RESILIENT
EU FARMING
SYSTEMS **Farm**

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T4.3: Assessing how policies enable or constrain the resilience of the private fruit and vegetable farming system in the Mazovian region (Poland).

An application of the Resilience Assessment Tool (ResAT)

Work Performed by P15, Institute of Rural and Agricultural Development of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland (IRWiR PAN)

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Main farming system specific challenges

The case study is conducted on Polish private fruit and vegetable farms, regarding economic, environmental and social risks. The vulnerability to economic risks is assessed in the relation to declining prices due to the Russian embargo, variations in prices and lack of labor for seasonal and labor intensive work. In 2014, the Russian Federation have put the embargo on Polish agricultural sector. As a result, import of (among others) Polish fruits and vegetables was suspended. The Embargo resulted also in lowering the volume of Polish export of fruits and vegetables to countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (Klepacka, Florkowski, 2016). The embargo affected also the prices of fruits and vegetables. Also other factors, such as the Single European Market or price changes on the world market, influence fruit and vegetable prices in Poland. The prices are subject to seasonal supply fluctuations also, mostly due to the fruits' sensitivity to unfavorable agro meteorological conditions, which contribute to crop failure (Bieniek-Majka, 2017). In the years 2008-2016, price volatility for fruits amounted to 22.3% and in case of vegetables it was at the level of 13.1% (Czyżewski, Bieniek-Majka, Czakowski, 2018). Vulnerability to environmental risks will be assessed in the relation to increasing incidents of extreme weather phenomena, such as hail, freeze, drought, and to hydrological instability, infestation of trees by pests and fungal diseases. For example, floods in 2010 and May frosts in 2011 caused the rapid price increase of fruits and vegetables (Czyżewski, Bieniek-Majka, Czakowski, 2018). Vulnerability to social risk relates to changes in preferences of consumers. The fruits represent a negligible part in the pattern of consumption, and with low incomes, the spending on them can be limited. Another key factor forming the volume of the consumed fruit is their prices which influence the periodical changes in demand for particular species. These changes are partly attributed to variations in domestic production highly dependent on atmospheric conditions (Stolarska, 2014). Another factor influencing the resilience of the system is that in the case study region of Mazovia and Podlasie, there is the lowest crop insurance uptake in the country (Wąs, Kobus, 2018). Linkages of farms to processing industry, as well as to agribusiness organizations, will be discussed in interviews. The proposed farming system to be studied is a private family fruit and vegetable farming in the Mazovia and Podlasie region, which includes Mazowieckie, Podlaskie, Lubelskie i Łódzkie voivodeships. According to FADN, there were 791 farms of this type in the whole Poland, but in the region of Mazovia and Podlasie - 451.

List of selected policy documents

Ecorys, Institute for European Environmental Policy & Wageningen University. (2016).

Mapping and analysis of the implementation of the CAP. Executive Summary. Brussels.

European Commission. (2013a). CAP Reform – an explanation of the main elements.

Brussels.

European Commission. (2013b). Overview of CAP Reform 2014-2020. Agricultural Policy Perspectives Brief No 5. Brussels.

European Commission. (2014). Summary of the Partnership Agreement for Poland, 2014-2020. Brussels.

European Commission. (2017a). Agriculture. A partnership between Europe and farmers.

The EU's common agricultural policy (CAP): for our food, for our countryside, for our environment. Luxembourg.

European Commission. (2017b). Cap Explained. Direct payments for farmers 2015-2020.

Luxembourg.

Kantor Management Consultants S.A. (2015). Synthesis of ex ante evaluations of Rural Development Programmes 2014-2020. Executive summary. Brussels.

Ministerstwo Rolnictwa i Rozwoju Wsi. (2018). Priorytety Ministerstwa Rolnictwa i Rozwoju Wsi na lata 2018-2019. Warszawa.

Analysis

Question	Scale (0-5)	Arguments
Robustness		
1a. To what extent is a focus on the short-term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	1	The CAP goals usually relate to time scope longer than one year, so they do not enable short-term focus. The only short term goal expressed in analyzed documents is the intention of mitigating risks related to uncertainty of agricultural commodity markets and environmental risks, over which farmers have no control (EC, 2017b, p.3).
1b. To what extent is a focus on the short-term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	3	The short-term focus of CAP instruments is fairly enabled and related to direct payments, for which farmers can apply every year and which are limited each year by the annual allocation (EC, 2017b, p.4). Other instruments are usually targeted for the time period over one year.
2a. To what extent is protection of the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	3	Protection of status quo is fairly enabled by the CAP goals. Some goals are targeted on maintaining the current levels of production, and to ensure that farmers continue working on the land and have a degree of stability in revenues. Other goals are stated to ensure that rural communities remain in good economic condition (EC, 2013a, p.3). There are also goals targeted on strengthening the

position of farmers in the food chain, for example by encouraging the formation of producers organizations or taking actions for strengthening the brand of Polish food products abroad (EC, 2017a, p.12). The Polish Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development is declaring determinacy in keeping the model of agriculture based on family farms, by ensuring special protection and support of them (MRiRW, 2018, p. 2). Another area of protecting status quo is support for keeping the share of domestic plant varieties. On the other hand, linking of direct payments to certain products is only optional for countries and limited by the EU, and more goals in analyzed documents are targeted on improving the farming than to maintaining status quo.

2b. To what extent is protection of the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?

4 Instruments of the CAP enable protection of status quo. Over three thousands products are under protection of EU by registration as “geographical indications” (EC, 2017a, p. 9). In Poland, a Program for supporting domestic plant varieties was launched (MRWiR, 2018, p. 11). Limited amounts of payments linked, for example, to specific products or sectors, are an option for Member States (EC, 2013b, p.7). The fruit and vegetable market is one of nine indicated in Polish Program of main agricultural markets development for years 2016-2020, which, for example, enables special provisions for cultivation of tomatoes or strawberries (MRiRW, 2018, p. 18). There are aid amounts for farming in mountain areas and other areas facing natural and other specific constraints. There are also payments attributed to the first hectares of the farms which provide more targeted support for small and medium-sized farms. Ten Member

States (including Poland), used an opportunity to introduce the redistributive payment (EC, 2017b, p.7). Market measures and income support are funded fully from EU budget, even though rural development programs have to be co-financed by Member States. However, the CAP is turning into promoting sustainable farming by linking 30% of national envelopes to provisions for sustainable practices, which is an incentive for farmers to modify their practices (EC, 2013a, p.1). Policy not supporting status quo, is a development policy, helping developing countries to sell agricultural goods on preferential terms.

3a. To what extent is the development of buffer resources enabled or constrained by the policy goals?

5 The goals of CAP are very enabling for the development of buffer resources. According to the European Commission, farmers should be rewarded for the services delivered for the public by stable income support, independent of market fluctuations and it should be ensured that they can make a decent living, and at the same time invest in farms (EC, 2013b, P. 5). Additionally, young people can get funds for starting a farm (EC, 2017a, p. 8). In Poland, a project for improvement of stability and continuity of agricultural production in the periodic water shortage or excess was launched. It is based on support for construction, reconstruction and proper use of drainage devices for improvement of production conditions, increase of water retention and achieving environmental effects (MRiRW, 2018, p. 31). Buffer resources are also considered a mean to provide stable, varied and safe food supply for citizens (EC, 2017b, p. 1).

<p>3b. To what extent is the development of buffer resources enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>Policy instruments are very enabling for the development of buffer resources. Direct payments are the major source of support offered by the CAP (72% of the budget), serving nearly 7 million farms in the EU and representing an important share of their agricultural income (EC, 2017b, p.1). Up to 70% of Direct Payments in Member States are dedicated to the Basic Payment Scheme, together with Young Farmer top-ups, Less Favoured Area top-ups (up to 5% of national envelope), Redistributive Payment for small farms, and “coupled” payments (EC, 2013a, p.1). The payments are limited to those, who are engaged actively in agricultural activities. Young farmers entering the sector can get additional first pillar payment, possibly complemented by start-up aid under the second pillar. Also, a new crisis reserve of 400 million EUR per year in 2011 prices was introduced to secure financial resources needed in case of crisis (EC, 2013b, p.6). In Poland, a fund for stabilization of fruits and vegetables producers incomes is being developed (EC, 2017b, p.1). There is one major change in buffer resources policy, which is introducing instruments for provision of public goods, such as food safety, the climate and environment, protection of water resources, animal welfare and condition of the farmland. However, in real terms CAP funding decreased, compared to the previous period (EC, 2017a, p.7).</p>
<p>4a. To what extent are other modes of managing risks enabled or constrained by the policy goals?</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Other modes of managing risks are enabled by the CAP goals. The current CAP maintains two pillars but increases the link between them to better integrate policy support and enhance the safety net measures to deal with potential threats and disturbances (EC, 2013b, p.1). The mutual funds and insurance schemes</p>

allow farmers to respond better to market instabilities and volatility of prices. Polish Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development has a goal of stabilizing the main agricultural markets, to ensure food safety in the country. It aims to increase the intake of insurance of farm facilities and yields. The Single Common Market Organisation aims to improve competitiveness of the EU agriculture on world markets and provide safety net for farmers against external uncertainties. It coexists with direct payments and risk management provisions under rural development programs (EC, 2013a, p.5). In Poland there is a national program for reducing the risk related to usage of plant protection products, which aims to promote non-chemical plant protection methods and reduction of pesticides use (MRiRW, 2018, p. 23). Phytosanitary law and rules for fighting and preventing the spread of dangerous organisms, aim to prevent losses in crops and other regulations, for example related to soil liming, prevent the chemical degradation of soils. Support for beekeeping also aims at reducing risks which can affect fruit and vegetable production.

4b. To what extent are other modes of managing risks enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?

4 The policy instruments enable other modes of managing risks. While grants and loans play major role in helping farmers, instruments such as financial guarantee schemes or insurances are also available within European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) (EC, 2017a, p.12). The Crisis Reserve, amounting to 400 million Euros in 2011 prices, enables the European Commission to take emergency measures in response to market disturbances or drop in prices. The

modernized crop and weather insurance available in pillar II is extended by income stabilization option, allowing to pay out up to 70% of losses in income drops by 30% (EC, 2013a, p.7). In Poland, the action plan for diminishing the risk related to plant protection products and a program of financing soil liming are being implemented (MRiRW, 2018, p. 28). The Polish Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development is preparing Polish producers to changes also by information and consulting activities.

Adaptability

1a. To what extent is a focus on the middle-long term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	2	The CAP goals slightly enable middle-long-term focus, due to the fact, that goals usually relate to long time scope. Few of them have middle-term focus, such as measures for encouraging potential new entrants to take up farming (EC, 2017b, p.9).
1b. To what extent is a focus on the middle-long term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	3	The CAP instruments fairly enable middle-long-term focus, mostly within pillar II. Rural development programs generally extend over several years (EC, 2017b, p.11). Additional payment for Young Farmers, compulsory for all Member states, is available for a period of maximum 5 years from the moment of taking over as the head of the farm holding. The scope of introducing the Greening payment also has a middle-term focus. In years 1 & 2, the penalty for failing to respect their rules are not applied, in third year they amount to 20%, and in the fourth year the maximum penalty will reach 25% (EC, 2013a, p.3).

2a. To what extent is flexibility enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	4	The CAP goals enable flexibility. Member states or regions can design their own multi-annual programs in response to needs of their rural areas on the basis of the menu of measures available at the EU level (EC, 2013a, p.6). The new rules of the second pillar are more flexible than in the previous programming period. The goal of such changes is to leave the Member countries more freedom in fitting their agricultural policy to regional needs.
2b. To what extent is flexibility enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	3	The instruments enable flexibility fairly. Member States have the possibility of transferring up to 15% of the national envelope for Pillar I to Pillar II (EC, 2013a, p.4). However, the amount of EU funds dedicated to Pillar II was cut by 7.6%, while Pillar I by 1.8% (EC, 2013b, p.3). These funds do not need to be co-funded. Active farmers have access to compulsory schemes, as well as voluntary ones, if established at the national level. The exact threshold varies between countries. Depending on the choices made by national authorities, the basic payment is between 12% and 68% of the national budget (EC, 2017b, p.7). The basic payment is applied or as a Basic Payment Scheme (BPS) or as Single Area Payment Scheme (SAPS). The member state may opt for differences in the value of entitlements. The allocation for direct payments dedicated to coupled support, young farmers, small farmers etc. depend on particular Member State, so the shares of funding allocated to different schemes may vary significantly between the countries, depending on their issues of most concern and national farming conditions (Kantor Management Consultants, 2015, p. 5), but within regulatory and budgetary limits (like maximum 8% for coupled support

or maximum of 2% for young farmers). Regional Development programs have to be build based on at least four out of the six common EU priorities. 30% of the national allocation has to be dedicated to greening payment (EC, 2017b, p.8). The standards, which farmers have to meet in order to obtain full support, are set on national level. Countries have 5% margin of flexibility in setting a ratio of permanent grassland to agricultural land (EC, 2017b, p.8). The already introduced environmentally beneficial practices can replace the basic requirements.

3a. To what extent are variety and tailor-made responses enabled or constrained by the policy goals?

4 Variety and tailor-made responses are enabled by the CAP goals. The CAP is not only about feeding the population, but also contributes to other key objectives of the European Union, such as boosting jobs and growth in the farming sector, increasing sustainability and targeting climate change (EC, 2017b, p.12). The incentives for sustainable and environmentally friendly farming diminish the environmental risks (EC, 2017a, p.4). The environmental goals try to adjust the farm activities by variation in response to the knowledge of environmental degradation, while the system can continue with its important functionalities, such as producing food, along the same trajectory. The Member States can design thematic sub-programs, in order to give special attention to issues such as young farmers, small farms, mountain areas, women in rural areas climate change, biodiversity or short supply chains (EC, 2013a, p.6). In the first pillar, the diversity of agriculture, agronomic production potential, socio-economic needs and environmental issues, such as climate change, are

acknowledged (EC, 2013b, p.5). The CAP policy documents express the goals related to improving environmental sustainability of agriculture and challenges related to climate change mitigation and adaptation, including developing the resilience to different disasters, such as floods, droughts or fires. Other goals include increasing competitiveness of Polish agriculture and balanced territorial development (EC, 2014, p.2). The projects funded by the rural development programs can have goals related to on-farm investments and modernization, young farmers, agro-environmental issues, conversion to organic farms, agro-tourism, and village renewal or internet provision. So the prioritized activities can be of economic, environmental, as well as territorial nature.

3b. To what extent are variety and tailor-made responses enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?

4 Variety and tailor-made responses are enabled by the CAP instruments. National or regional programs of development are designed to address specific needs and challenges of rural areas in those countries and regions (EC, 2017a, p.7). The II pillar provides a more diverse approach than in previous programming period, by changing “axes” into 6 broad priorities and their focus areas. Within the pillar II, different instruments aim to help the farm sector to adapt to new trends and technologies and become more efficient, cost effective and adaptive to various challenges. For small farms, a funding for advice and economic development is available, and for young farmers – start up aid. Instruments of the CAP also allow grants for non-agricultural start-ups and development of small and microbusinesses (EC, 2013a, p.7), which can be a possibility for farmers, whose agricultural business is not efficient. At least 30% of the budget has to be

reserved for voluntary measures, which are beneficial for environment and mitigate the negative results of climate change (EC, 2013b, p.7). The instruments are varied and include agri-environmental climate measures, organic farming, Areas of Natural Constraints, Natura 2000 areas, forestry measures, and investments beneficial for environment and climate.

4a. To what extent is social learning enabled or constrained by the policy goals?

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The policy goals fairly enable social learning. The European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity & Sustainability is the key theme. Measures within this partnership include knowledge transfer and cooperation between agriculture and research to enhance technological transfer to farmers, as well as with other stakeholders, such as agro-business, administrations etc. (EC, 2013a, p.7). There are goals of creating knowledge-based agriculture and strengthening advisory services. There is support for bottom-up forms of integration of producers, such as producer groups, cooperatives and other organizations, with one of the goals to share knowledge (EC, 2017a, p.11). Cooperatives are believed to build social integrity in rural areas, but in Poland the agricultural chambers, with mandatory membership, are considered by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development as the most important organization for agricultural self-government in rural areas (MRiRW, 2018, p. 40) and they do not focus on social learning. All in all, the social learning is mostly an additional goal next to other priorities.

4b. To what extent is social learning enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?

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Social learning is enabled by the CAP instruments fairly. The possibility of acquiring the higher co-funding rate for measures supporting knowledge transfer and collaboration, supports the social learning: “The maximum EU co-funding rates will be up to 85% in less developed regions, the outermost regions and the smaller Aegean islands, 75% in transition regions, 63% in other transition regions and 53% in other regions for most payments, but can be higher for the measures supporting knowledge transfer, cooperation, the establishment of producer groups and organisations and young farmer installation grants, as well as for LEADER projects and for spending related to the environment and climate change under various measures” (EC, 2013a, p.6). LEADER projects in this programming period put a greater emphasis on awareness-rising. Policy instruments are accompanied by training and advisory measures (EC, 2013b, p.7). In Poland there is a Network for agricultural and rural innovations. Scientific institutes and public agricultural advisory units are cooperating with innovation action groups, agricultural businesses and other relevant organizations to implement innovations. Also, a program for scientific research on possibilities of development of insurances in agriculture was launched, which aims on suggesting solutions for farmers and creating new instruments. Funds are also dedicated to development of science serving ecological agriculture. Educational activities, related to use of renewable energy sources in the form of energetic cooperatives in rural areas, are under preparation. The project “Akademia Producenta i Eksportera” (Academy for Producer and Exporter)

is an instrument for distribution among local producers and exporters the information and promotion materials related to foreign trade markets for agricultural products, as well as institutional and organizational conditions of exporting Polish products (MRiRW, 2018, p. 39). These activities will include seminars and workshops. Presented actions are more focused on trainings and information than social learning, which is considered supplementary.

Transformability

1a. To what extent is a focus on the long term enabled or constrained by the policy goals?

3 The focus on the long term is fairly enabled by the CAP goals. The main long-term CAP objectives are safe and high quality food production, sustainable management of natural resources and balanced territorial development (EC, 2013b, p.2). Member States have the responsibility to set out future strategies for the agricultural sectors, which will ensure their efficiency, competitiveness and sustainability in the long-term. However, most of those goals are not specific. Only some goals are more specific, such as providing training for almost 4 mln participants and 1.4 mln advisory sessions with a focus on economic and environmental performance of farms or providing improved internet services and infrastructure to 18 mln rural citizens till 2020 (EC, 2013b, p.2). Too general goals may make it more difficult to really transform the farming systems. Additionally, some of those goals, such as safe and high quality food production, or a sustainable management of natural resources can also be seen as assuring that the system can maintain the desired levels of output in the future, without

		transforming itself and therefore facilitating robustness by protecting status quo, instead of setting new goals for the future development. That is why the specification of those goals would be necessary to assess if the CAP goals focus on the long term transformation in a higher than fair level.
1b. To what extent is a focus on the long term enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	2	Focus on the long term is only slightly enabled by the CAP instruments. Relatively long-term oriented instruments are related to national rural development programs, which include actions undertaken in seven years period (EC, 2013b, p.9). However, according to Ecorys et al (2016, p. 9), Member States did not document a joined up, coherent strategy on which to base their choices about the implementation of the CAP.
2a. To what extent is the dismantling of incentives that support the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	2	The dismantling of incentives that support the status quo is only slightly enabled by the CAP goals, because the key characteristics of the CAP remained untouched by the reform (EC, 2013b, p.9). In the examined documents, no expressed will of dismantling such incentives was found.
2b. To what extent is the dismantling of incentives that support the status quo enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	3	The CAP instruments fairly enable dismantling of incentives that support the status quo. The CAP expenditure for market management, such as export refunds and intervention purchases is dropping, although it is important to notice that the main drop took place in the previous programming periods, from over 90% in 1992 to 5% in 2013, which gives a significant difference of 85 percentage points within 11 years (EC, 2013b, p.4). However, the remaining fund for market management may be seen as still slightly constraining the other modes of risk

		management instruments, and supporting the status quo is supported farming systems.
3a. To what extent is in-depth learning enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	1	In-depth learning is not enabled by the policy goals. There are no goals expressed in examined documents, which would be related to in-depth learning. The goals related to learning do not concern changes in paradigms, radically new frames not broad involvement of stakeholders (except research centers).
3b. To what extent is in-depth learning enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	1	In-depth learning is not enabled by the policy instruments. There are no instruments indicated in examined documents, which would be related to implementation of in-depth learning.
4a. To what extent is the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations enabled or constrained by the policy goals?	1	The enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations are not enabled by the CAP goals. One of the goals for pillar II is fostering knowledge transfer and innovation, but it is a broad statement, with no focus on niche innovations. More focus is put to knowledge transfer, for example from scientific institutes or consultants to farmers, which is more an investment in adaptability - social learning (EC, 2013b, p.6).
4a. To what extent is the enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations enabled or constrained by the policy instruments?	1	The enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations are not enabled by any specific instruments of the CAP. The existing instruments do not leave neither room nor resources for experimenting and niche innovations. The self-organization instruments are created mainly for other reasons than niche innovations.

ResAT Wheel – Goals

ROBUSTNESS: The CAP goals usually relate to time scope longer than one year, so they do not enable short term focus. The only short term goal expressed in analyzed documents is the intention of mitigating risks related to uncertainty of markets and environmental risks (EC, 2017b). Protection of status quo is fairly enabled (EC, 2013a). MRiRW is declaring keeping the model of agriculture based on family farms, by ensuring special support. The goals of CAP are very enabling for the development of buffer resources (EC, 2013b). Farmers are rewarded for their services by stable income support. Also other modes of managing risks are enabled by the CAP goals. Mutual funds and insurance schemes allow farmers to respond better to market and price instabilities (EC, 2017a). MRiRW aims to stabilize the main agricultural markets, and increase the intake of farm facilities and yields insurance.

ADAPTABILITY: The CAP goals slightly enable middle-long-term focus, although goals usually relate to long time scope. Few of them have middle-term focus, such as measures for encouraging potential new entrants to take up farming (EC, 2017b). The CAP goals enable flexibility. Member States can design their own multi-annual programs in response to needs of their rural areas on the basis of the menu of measures available at the EU level. The new rules of the second pillar are more flexible than in the previous programming periods (EC, 2013a). Variety and tailor-made responses are enabled by the CAP goals (EC, 2014). The Member States can design thematic sub-programs, to give special attention to issues such as young farmers, small farms, mountain areas, women in rural areas climate change, biodiversity or short supply chains. Social learning is enabled fairly. There are goals of creating knowledge-based agriculture and strengthening advisory services, but the social learning is mostly an additional goal to other priorities (EC, 2017a).

TRANSFORMABILITY: The focus on the long term is fairly enabled by the CAP goals. Member States have the responsibility to set out future strategies for the agricultural sectors, which will ensure their efficiency, competitiveness and sustainability in the long-term (EC, 2017a). However, most of those goals are not specific. The dismantling of incentives that support the status quo is only slightly enabled by the CAP goals, because the key characteristics of the CAP remained untouched by the reform (EC, 2013b). In the examined documents there is no expressed will of dismantling such incentives. In-depth learning is not enabled by the policy goals. The goals related to learning do not concern changes in paradigms or radically new frames. The enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations is not enabled by the CAP goals (EC, 2013b).

ResAT Wheel – Instruments

ROBUSTNESS: The short-term focus of CAP instruments is fairly enabled and related to direct payments, for which farmers can apply every year and which are limited by the annual allocation (EC, 2017b). Instruments of the CAP enable protection of status quo. Market measures and income support are funded fully from EU budget. Ten Member States (including Poland), used the option of the redistributive payment. In Poland, a Program for supporting domestic plant varieties was launched (MRiRW, 2018). Policy instruments are very enabling for the development of buffer resources. Direct payments are the major source of support offered by the CAP (72% of the budget) (EC, 2017b). The policy instruments enable also other modes of managing risks. While grants and loans play major role in helping farmers, financial guarantee schemes or insurances are also available (EC, 2013a).

ADAPTABILITY: The CAP instruments fairly enable middle-long-term focus, mostly within pillar II (EC, 2013a). Rural development programs extend over several years. The instruments enable flexibility fairly. Shares of funding allocated to different schemes vary between the countries, but within regulatory and budgetary limits (like max. 8% for coupled support or max. of 2% for young farmers) (EC, 2017b). Variety and tailor-made responses are enabled by the CAP instruments. National programs of development are designed to address specific needs and challenges of their rural areas (EC, 2017a). The II pillar provides a more diverse approach than in previous programming period, by changing “axes” into 6 broad priorities and their focus areas. Within the pillar II, different instruments aim to help the farm sector to adapt to new trends and technologies and become more efficient, cost effective and adaptive to various challenges. Social learning is enabled by the CAP instruments fairly. Instruments are more focused on trainings and information than social learning, which is considered supplementary (EC, 2013b).

TRANSFORMABILITY: Focus on the long term is only slightly enabled by the CAP instruments. Only national rural development programs include actions undertaken in seven years period (EC, 2013b). Instruments fairly enable dismantling of incentives that support the status quo. The expenditure for market management is dropping significantly, although the main drop took place in the previous programming periods, from over 90% in 1992 to 5% in 2013, which gives a significant difference of 85 percentage points within 11 years. There are no instruments indicated in examined documents, which would be related to implementation of in-depth learning. The enhancement and acceleration of niche innovations are not enabled by any specific instruments of the CAP.

GOALS

INSTRUMENTS

The comparison of goals and instruments

In general, the transformability is the least supported aspect of resilience. Especially in-depth learning and niche innovations seem to be heavily neglected by the CAP (EC, 2013b). Robustness and adaptability are relatively balanced in case of goals, but in case of instruments the dominance of robustness can be observed, as there is a shift towards short term focus and protecting the status quo in Polish agriculture. The short-term focus of CAP instruments is fairly enabled and related to direct payments, for which farmers can apply every year and which are limited by the annual allocation (EC, 2017b). Buffer resources in case of both goals and instrument, seem to be relatively strongly supported. Farmers are rewarded for their services by stable income support and direct payments are the major source of support offered by the CAP (72% of the budget) (EC, 2017b). Also other modes of managing risks are enabled by the CAP goals. Mutual funds and insurance schemes allow farmers to respond better to the market and price instabilities (EC, 2017a). MRiRW aims to stabilize the main agricultural markets, and increase the intake of farm facilities and yields insurance.

Another noticeable feature of the wheels is that they show relatively similarly the scores for three different aspects of resilience: robustness, adaptability and transformability. However there are some differences between them. The robustness is more supported by the CAP instruments than by the goals, especially in case of short term focus and protecting the status quo. The adaptability is similarly rated, however in the case of instruments, middle term focus has slightly greater importance, mostly within pillar II (EC, 2013a), and flexibility, to small extent, but loses its importance, due to the regulatory and budgetary limits (such as maximum 8% for coupled support or maximum of 2% for young farmers) (EC, 2017b). The level of transformability does not change significantly; Dismantling status quo slightly increases the importance in terms of instruments, compared to goals. National programs of development can be designed to address specific needs and challenges of their rural areas (EC, 2017a). The long-term focus loses the CAP support to some extent. While it is fairly enabled by the CAP goals, due to the fact that the Member States have the responsibility to set out future strategies for the agricultural sectors (EC, 2017a), the general character of guidelines leads to the situation, where Member States do not document a joined up, coherent strategy on which they base choices about the implementation of the CAP (Ecorys et al., 2016).

Stakeholder check

A focus group was organized in order to validate and enrich the outcomes, and increase the trustworthiness of the qualitative data analysis. The stakeholders have been selected based on their merits related to the horticulture sector and/or the CAP policy. The selected 15 stakeholders were selected and approached via e-mail invitation to take part in the focus group. There were seven participants: two representatives of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, one representative of the fruit farmers' organization, three academic horticulture experts, and one academic CAP expert.

The perspectives of stakeholders varied depending on the issue. They agreed with most of the arguments and the ResAT tool was considered useful, however some academic stakeholders expressed concerns about the scoring of data – that it is not clear how to score particular quotations, as well as, it is not sure to what extent the quantitative aspect, related to the number of quotations, affect the final score. It was mentioned that the tool is more useful for the macro level analysis, due to its loose connection to particular sectors. The stakeholders expressed interest in bottom-up analysis and comparison of the results of both research.

The stakeholders generally agreed to the arguments presented in the ResAT. They shared mostly their experience related to the implementation aspects of the CAP. They pointed out, that the horticulture sector is quite unique in Poland and in Europe. It receives relatively little support in direct payments, comparing to other farming sectors, due to small average size of farms. It forces the sector to adapt to the market and increase its' innovativeness. In the CAP, one of the problems with supporting the innovations is lack of precise definition, what can be considered as an innovation. It causes serious problem in supporting innovations through the Rural Development Program. The problem of the quality of the EU regulations was brought up several times by stakeholders, not only in case of the innovations. In case of horticulture, according to stakeholders, also important is the support for organizations, which is available in the Pillar I. It can be a source of increasing adaptability and the innovations, mostly in middle- and short-term (not big enough to support transformability, but rather adaptability). However, the cooperation and creation of cooperatives and producers groups is very ineffective in Poland.

It was also elaborated that there are differences between the situation of Polish fruit and Polish vegetable sector – there are not homogeneous –in terms of supply-demand instabilities and organizational structure. Especially the fruit sector is very low organized, which makes it even more difficult to use the available in the CAP funds by the sector. It is hard to provide the necessary information flow, so that small farmers know, how they can use funds other than direct payments, which consist on average only around 4% of general incomes of horticulture farms. Lack of information and education is often the reason for a small uptake in different instruments. Increasing complexity of the CAP requires more educational activities, to avoid difficulties in the implementation. Otherwise the regulations which might seem supportive might in reality have very little impact. For example, in the case of Poland, the insurances are not enough utilized tool for risk mitigation offered by the CAP, especially due to inefficiency of implementation. However the CAP is not effective in supporting education in Polish agriculture.

Stakeholders agreed that the buffer resources, protecting status quo and other forms of risk management are the most supported areas. The opinions were divided regarding the influence of those characteristics of robustness on the farming systems. Some stakeholders suggested that the adaptability is not enough supported, others claimed that the risk management is the reason for the CAP existence and therefore strongly supported, especially related to the climate-related risks. The interesting idea was that the less buffer resources are included in the agricultural policy (as for example in the US), the more needed are the other forms of risk management.

The stakeholders agreed with most of the challenges listed for the sector. The importance of the Russian embargo is mostly important for the fruit sector, which comes from the fact, that 80% of Polish fruit sector consists of apples cultivation, and Polish apples were mostly exported to the East (other fruits mostly to the Western countries). Among vegetables, only cabbages are to high extend exported to the East, and therefore got affected by the embargo (40% of production on Eastern markets export).

The stakeholders expressed, that it is not surprising, that the transformability is not supported, due to the fact, that it is seen as risky. The main goal of the CAP is the preservation of social and production structure. However, the support of social structure might play a dominant role, and stabilization of incomes does not necessarily mean the

stabilization of production, because it teaches the farmers to adapt not to the market and increase competitiveness, but how to adapt to the CAP regulations and support.

Another important issue brought up by the stakeholders is the continuous growth in energy prices, which is affecting and will continue to affect the horticulture sector even stronger in upcoming years. Other interesting remark was that the Ukraine starts to introduce traditionally Polish varieties of apples, which might in nearest future increase a competition for this sector.

The important issue pointed out during the discussion is the problem of the supply instability, which is an important economic thread, especially for fruit farming, due to lack of stabilizing tools, but was not included in the initial identification of main farming system specific challenges. The issue was added to the description. Even relatively small decrease in production results in large price increase, and vice versa, the increase in production leads to the rapid decrease in prices. This year the problem was so significant that 50-60% of chokeberry and around 20% of currants were not even picked from the fields, because the prices were so low, that that they could not cover the cost of the labor force picking those fruits. The vegetable market is more stable due to its' higher level of organization and implementation of minimum and maximum. However the market of fresh vegetables is less stable than the processed ones, but still not as vulnerable to supply instability, as the fruit sector. Most of the countries have fixed limits of production, but they are not applied in Poland in case of fruits, due to lack of the requirement of signing agreements between producers and processors, protecting both producers from to low prices, as well as processors from very high ones, which could endanger their business activity. It is a significant difficulty for this sector. Farmers use diversification of production as the risk management method.

Stakeholders pointed out also, that in Poland the ROPs and the CAP are not related. We need to create a mix of policies to achieve better outcomes. Additional benefit of that would be the change in mentality. It would enforce the national policy for agriculture. Lack of supplementing of the CAP from other policies is a big mistake. For example, the education should be conducted on all stages of the value chain. Currently we do not have instruments connecting farmers and consumers.

Overall analysis

The main conclusion from the analysis is that on the level of instruments, the CAP is more focused on robustness than on the level of goals, where there is more balance between robustness and adaptability. Both on the goals and the instruments level, transformability is the least supported from all of the three resilience capabilities.

Taking into account the challenges of the horticulture sector, the CAP does not sufficiently answer the economic challenges of the sector. It does not offer solutions for the price volatility due to the production changes, and the offered buffer resources do not always cover the financial burden related to that problem. The other forms of risk management, such as insurances, are enabled by the CAP, however, as stated in the stakeholder check, their implementation in Poland was relatively slow and the intake is very insufficient, due to the lack of awareness among the farmers of those insurances importance and availability. Productivity in farming is heavily related to the environmental factors, so the instruments related to mitigation of climate risks should be also more efficiently implemented. All in all, the robustness, although supported by the CAP, could be supported way more effectively, if the implementation of the instruments would be more intensified in the sector.

Better implementation requires improvement of educational activities. Social education is only fairly enabled by the CAP, and as the stakeholder check suggests, it is not sufficiently implemented to meet the needs of the sector. Also other characteristics of adaptability are supported by the CAP on a moderate level, both in case of goals and the instruments.

For the horticulture sector, the needs for in-depth learning and supporting niche innovations are heavily neglected by the CAP policy, both in case of the goals and the instruments. The sector is relatively innovative, although the CAP does not support this process, and do not support spreading niche innovations and good practices among farmers. The CAP instruments also not sufficiently support the long-term focus. For the horticulture farming system, which is one of the least benefitting from the direct payments, the support of adaptability and transformability seems to be vital for its development.

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Annex: Analysis of the policy documents

Type of resilience	Key characteristics	Relevant texts for policy goals	Relevant texts for policy instruments
Robustness	1. Short term	Farmers also have to cope with the special characteristics of agricultural commodity markets. Everybody needs food to survive, but demand does not change significantly if prices fall, as might be the case with other products. This means that farmers cannot rely on simply selling more of their output to compensate for lower prices. In addition, food production processes are long: for example, it takes two years for a dairy cow to reach the stage where it produces milk. These factors can have a significant impact on farmers' incomes, and yet they have virtually no control over them. (EC, 2017b, p.3)	The overall amount of direct payments to farmers in any member state is limited each year by the size of that country's annual allocation (EC, 2017b, s.4) Farmers may apply for direct payments every year (EC, 2017b, p.5)
	2. Protecting the status quo	In order to maintain current levels of production in sectors or regions where specific types of farming or sectors undergo	the introduction of a "Greening Payment" where 30% of the available national envelope is linked to the provision of certain sustainable

difficulties and are important for economic and/or social and/or environmental reasons (EC, 2013a, p.3)

in many countries, the major concern was to minimise the changes in support provided to the agricultural sector compared to the previous CAP (Ecorys et al., 2016, p. 5)

it appears that the rationale for the implementation choices in Pillar 1 is more influenced by the ambition to “maintain the status quo” than by a strategy related to the three CAP objectives (Ecorys et al., 2016, p. 6).

The CAP provides funds to ensure that rural communities in vulnerable areas remain in good economic health and do not gradually disappear. (EC, 2017a, p.8)

the CAP gives farmers financial assistance to ensure that they continue working the land (EC, 2017a, p.10)

farming practices means that a significant share of the subsidy will in future be linked to rewarding farmers for the provision of environmental public goods (EC, 2013a, p.1)

In order to maintain current levels of production in sectors or regions where specific types of farming or sectors undergo difficulties and are important for economic and/or social and/or environmental reasons, Member States will have the option of providing limited amounts of "coupled" payments, i.e. a payment linked to a specific product. This will be limited to up to 8% of the national envelope, or up to 13% if the current level of coupled support in a Member State is higher than 5%. (EC, 2013a, p.3)

Mountain areas: For mountain areas and farmland above 62° N, aid amounts can be up to 450 €/ha (increased from 250 €/ha); Other areas facing natural & other specific constraints: New delimitation for Areas with

The CAP increasingly helps farmers to strengthen their bargaining position vis-à-vis other players in the food chain. (EC, 2017a, p.12)

The EU helps farmers by encouraging: the formation of producer organisations: these allow farmers to form groups so that they can sell their products collectively, enabling them to exert greater market power within the food chain; other forms of cooperation to give farmers more leverage in the marketplace and raise profit margins and competitiveness. (EC, 2017a, p.12)

Member states may continue to link (or couple) a limited amount of direct payments to certain products. The aim of this type of support is to maintain the level of production in regions or in sectors undergoing difficulties and that are particularly important for economic, social or environmental reasons. (EC, 2017b, p.9)

Natural Constraints (ANC) with effect from 2018 at the latest based on 8 biophysical criteria; Member States retain flexibility to define up to 10% of their agricultural area for specific constraints to preserve or improve the environment (EC, 2013a, p.7)

A payment can be attributed to the first hectares of the farms, to provide more targeted support to small and medium-sized farms. A specific and simplified support scheme for small farmers will substantially facilitate their access to direct payments and reduce their administrative burden. Member States may also grant limited coupled support to secure the future of potentially vulnerable sectors. (EC, 2013b, p.7)

In addition Member States will have further possibilities to rebalance payments with the introduction of the redistributive payment, voluntary capping and degressivity (reduction) of payments, beyond the mandatory cuts

Ensuring a degree of stability to farm revenues and supporting on-farm investments through the CAP is vital not just for farmers but for the whole food industry. (EC, 2017b, p.12)

Jesteśmy zdecydowani utrzymywać model rolnictwa oparty na gospodarstwach rodzinnych, które zostały przez nas objęte szczególną pomocą i ochroną. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 2)

Realizacja Strategii promocji żywności wymaga podjęcia spójnych działań informacyjnych i promocyjnych, służących umocnieniu pozycji polskich produktów rolno-spożywczych za granicą i budowy silnej marki polskich produktów żywnościowych. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 25)

Szacuje się, że udział odmian krajowej hodowli w rynku nasiennym stanowi ok. 50%. W związku z tym niezbędne jest prowadzenie działań wspierających utrzymanie ich udziału

which will apply to the Basic Payment above a certain threshold (EC, 2013b, p.8)

In certain cases the effects of the decreased amounts under the BPS were mitigated through the use of other Pillar 1 instruments, such as the Redistributive Payment or Voluntary Coupled Support (VCS) (Ecorys et al., 2016, p. 5).

Market measures and income support are solely funded by the EU budget, whilst rural development measures are based on multiannual programming, co-financed by Member States. (EC, 2017a, p.7)

Traditional specialities have become increasingly popular and as a result, many farmers now sell their products directly to consumers at farmers' markets and process their own products to add local value. The EU supports these trends by offering protection for

i znaczenia w rynku nasiennym w Polsce. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 26)

Spółdzielczość wiejska w realiach polskiego rolnictwa i stanu rozwoju wsi jest niezbędna, aby mogły nadal funkcjonować średnie gospodarstwa rolne. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 40)

over 3 400 products by registering them as 'geographical indications'. (EC, 2017a, p.9)

Through its overseas development policy, the EU helps developing countries to sell their agricultural products in the EU. It does this by granting preferential access to its market. (EC, 2017a, p.14)

Ten member states have decided to opt for the redistributive payment (Belgium - Wallonia only, Bulgaria, Germany, France, Croatia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, United Kingdom - Wales only, plus Portugal from 2017). (EC, 2017b, p.7)

włączony został także Program wsparcia hodowli roślin w Polsce, którego celem głównym jest utrzymanie znaczenia na krajowym rynku nasiennym odmian hodowanych w Polsce. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 11)

Kontynuowane będzie wdrażanie opracowanego w MRiRW Programu rozwoju

głównych rynków rolnych w Polsce na lata 2016-2020, który koncentruje się na dziewięciu głównych rynkach rolnych, tj. rynkach: zbóż, rzepaku, wieprzowiny, wołowiny, drobiu, mleka i przetworów mlecznych, cukru owoców i warzyw oraz tytoniu. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 13)

płatności do pomidorów, płatności do truskawek (MRiRW, 2018, p. 18)

Z dniem 12 lipca 2017 r. weszła w życie ustawa z dnia 15 grudnia 2016 r. O przeciwdziałaniu nieuczciwemu wykorzystywaniu przewagi kontraktowej w obrocie produktami rolnymi i spożywczymi. Ustawa, w celu ochrony interesu publicznego, określa zasady przeciwdziałania praktykom polegającym na nieuczciwym wykorzystywaniu przewagi kontraktowej przez nabywców produktów rolnych lub spożywczych lub dostawców tych produktów. Stanowi ona jedną z szeregu inicjatyw

		ustawodawczych mających na celu wzmocnienie pozycji rolnika w łańcuchu dostaw żywności. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 30)
3. Buffer resources	<p>placing the joint provision of public and private goods at the core of policy. Farmers should be rewarded for the services they deliver to the wider public, such as landscapes, farmland biodiversity, climate stability even though they have no market value. (EC, 2013b, p.5)</p> <p>to ensure that EU farmers can make a reasonable living. (EC, 2017a, p.3)</p> <p>To remunerate farmers for this service to society as a whole, the EU provides farmers with income support. (EC, 2017a, p.4)</p> <p>Farmers can be adversely affected by climate change. The CAP provides them with financial assistance to adjust their farming methods and systems to cope with the effects of a changing climate. (EC, 2017a, p.4)</p>	<p>Member States will dedicate up to 70% of their Direct Payments national envelope to the new Basic Payment Scheme – minus and amounts committed for additional payments (Young Farmer top-ups, and other options such as Less Favoured Area top-ups, the Redistributive Payment) and "coupled" payments. (EC, 2013a, p.1)</p> <p>Member States (or regions) may grant an additional payment for areas with natural constraints (as defined under Rural Development rules) of up to 5% of the national envelope. (EC, 2013a, p.3)</p> <p>Farm restructuring / investment / modernisation: Grants still available – sometimes with higher support rates when linked to the EIP or joint projects; • Young farmers - A combination of measures can</p>

The main aims of the CAP are to improve agricultural productivity, so that consumers have a stable supply of affordable food, and to ensure that EU farmers can make a reasonable living. (EC, 2017a, p.6)

business uncertainties justify the important role that the public sector plays in ensuring income stability for farmers. (EC, 2017a, p.7)

Income support. Direct payments provide support to farm income and remunerate farmers for delivering public goods not normally paid for by the markets, such as taking care of the countryside. (EC, 2017a, p.7)

CAP helps young people to get started in farming with funds to buy land, machinery and equipment. (EC, 2017a, p.8)

aim is to help provide a decent standard of living for European farmers and agricultural

include business start-up grants (up to €70 000), general investments in physical assets, training and advisory services; • Small farmers: Business start-up aid up to €15 000 per small farm .(EC, 2013a, p.7)

In real terms CAP funding will decrease compared to the current period. .(EC, 2013b, p.3)

direct payments are the major source of support (EC, 2013b, p.4)

Therefore, a new policy instrument of the first pillar (greening) is directed to the provision of environmental public goods, which constitutes a major change in the policy framework. (EC, 2013b, p.5)

A new crisis reserve (of EUR 400 million per year in 2011 prices) is established to secure the financial resources needed in case of crisis, through deductions from direct payments, with unused amounts reimbursed

workers and a stable, varied and safe food supply for citizens. (EC, 2017b, p.1)

In an uncertain and unpredictable economic environment, direct payments provide a safety net for farmers. They are a stable source of income that is independent of market fluctuations, making a very important contribution to overall farm income for many farm households (EC, 2017b, p.3)

Nowe wyzwania dla producentów rolnych w zakresie zwiększenia skali produkcji przy obniżaniu nakładów finansowych i pracy oraz realizacji niszowej produkcji rolnej wymagają wzrostu nakładów na inwestycje w gospodarstwach rolnych. Wsparcie ze środków publicznych inwestycji (MRiRW, 2018, p. 30)

W ramach prac nad SOR, MriRW zgłosiło do realizacji zadanie pn. Woda dla rolnictwa. Celem projektu jest poprawa stabilności i ciągłości produkcji rolniczej w warunkach

to farmers in the consecutive budget years. (EC, 2013b, p.6)

direct payments are better targeted by limiting support to those who are actively engaged in agricultural activities (EC, 2013b, p.7)

from 2015, all young farmers entering the sector will have the opportunity to get an additional first pillar payment, which can still be complemented by a start-up aid under the second pillar. (EC, 2013b, p.7)

internal convergence within the Member States. Payments will no longer be based on uneven historical references of more than a decade ago but rather on a fairer and more converging per hectare payment at national or regional level. (EC, 2013b, p.8)

Under the new CAP, the targeting of Direct Payments has been strengthened, with the Member States' implementation choices having contributed to this: although compared

okresowych niedoborów i nadmiarów wody, w tym przede wszystkim wsparcie gospodarstw rodzinnych w budowie, odbudowie i prawidłowym wykorzystaniu urządzeń melioracyjnych dla poprawienia warunków produkcji, powiększenia retencji wodnej oraz osiągnięcia efektów środowiskowych. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 31)

to the previous CAP the total budget available has declined by about 1,8% for the entire programming period, a large proportion of the total budget is spent on Direct Payments (Ecorys et. al., 2016, p. 7).

Finally, as a share of the EU budget, the budget of the common agricultural policy has decreased very sharply over the past 30 years, from almost 75 % to less than 40 %. During this period 18 new Member States have joined the Union (more than doubling the number of farmers) and as a result the spending per farmer is much lower today than in the past. (EC, 2017a, p.7)

income support for farmers (so-called “direct payments”) (EC, 2017b, p.1)

direct payments, a key element of the policy that provides income support for farmers and promotes competitiveness, sustainability and environmentally-friendly farming practices. The lion’s share (72%) of the current EU farm

budget is dedicated to direct payments for European farmers. (EC, 2017b, p.1)

Direct payments benefit nearly 7 million farms throughout the European Union and often represent an important share of their agricultural income (on average, nearly half of farmers' income in the last ten years came from this direct support). (EC, 2017b, p.1)

Direct payments amount to approximately €293 billion for that period, or 72% of the overall budget allocated for the CAP. This equates to spending of more than €41 billion a year for direct payments. (EC, 2017b, p.2)

There is a link between CAP payments for farmers and the respect of other EU rules concerning food safety, animal health, plant health, the climate, the environment, the protection of water resources, animal welfare and the condition in which farmland is maintained. This link is known as cross-compliance. In order to receive the full amount

of direct payments for which they are eligible, farmers have to respect all these other rules. Failure to do so results in a cut in the level of support. The size of the cut depends on to what extent the farmer is in breach of the rules. (EC, 2017b, p.5)

The basic payment ensures basic income support for farmers engaged in agricultural activities. (EC, 2017b, p.7)

More than three quarters of farm holdings in the EU are small - below 10 ha - with the very large majority of those below 5ha. In order to address the specific situation of these farms, member states can apply the small farmers scheme (SFS), a simplified direct payment scheme granting a one-off payment to farmers who choose to participate. The maximum level of the payment is decided at the national level, but in any case may not exceed €1,250. (EC, 2017b, p.10)

		utworzony zostanie jeden fundusz stabilizacji przychodów producentów owoców i warzyw. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 15)
4. Other risk management measures	<p>Other amendments to the Single Common Market Organisation (CMO) rules aim to improve the market orientation of EU agriculture in light of increased competition on world markets, while providing an effective safety net for farmers in the context of external uncertainties (together with direct payments and options for risk management under rural development). The existing systems of public intervention and private storage aid are revised to be more responsive and more efficient (EC, 2013a, p.5)</p> <p>The new CAP maintains the two pillars, but increases the links between them, thus offering a more holistic and integrated approach to policy support. Specifically it introduces a new architecture of direct payments; better targeted, more equitable</p>	<p>new safeguard clauses are introduced for all sectors to enable the Commission to take emergency measures to respond to general market disturbances – such as the measures taken during the e-coli crisis in May-July 2011. These measures will be funded from a Crisis Reserve financed by annually reducing direct payments. Funds not used for crisis measures will be returned to farmers in the following year. (EC, 2013a, p.5)</p> <p>Risk management toolkit: Insurance & mutual funds – for crop & weather insurance, animal disease [currently available under Article 68 in the 1st Pillar] - extended to include income stabilisation option (which would allow a payout (up to 70% of losses) from a mutual fund if income drops by 30%) (EC, 2013a, p.7)</p>

and greener, an enhanced safety net and strengthened rural development. (EC, 2013b, p.1)

At the same time the new CAP also offers more responsive safety net measures and strengthens the EU's capacity for crisis management. This will be achieved by more efficient market measures to deal with potential threats of market disturbances and more flexible exceptional measures. (EC, 2013b, p.6)

the creation of mutual funds and insurance schemes to allow farmers to respond better to market instability or fast-falling prices (EC, 2017a, p.13)

ustabilizować podstawowe rynki rolne (MRiRW, 2018, p. 2)

zapewniamy Polakom bezpieczeństwo i suwerenność żywnościową kraju (MRiRW, 2018, p. 2)

A crisis reserve will be created every year for an amount of €400 million (in 2011 prices) by application of financial discipline. If the amount is not used for a crisis it will be reimbursed to farmers as direct payments in the following year. (EC, 2013a, p.8)

In addition, the second pillar offers a new risk-management toolkit including insurance schemes for crops, animals and plants, as well as mutual funds and an income stabilisation tool. (EC, 2013b, p.6)

Market measures: The European Commission can take measures to deal with difficult market situations such as a sudden drop in demand due to a health scare, or a fall in prices as a result of a temporary oversupply on the market. (EC, 2017a, p.7)

While grants and loans play a major role in helping farmers, other means are also

Upowszechnianie ubezpieczeń upraw rolnych i zwierząt gospodarskich oraz wypełnienie przez producentów rolnych obowiązku ubezpieczania budynków wchodzących w skład gospodarstwa rolnego oraz OC rolników zmniejszy ryzyko prowadzenia produkcji rolnej oraz zabezpieczy przed spadkiem dochodów, zapewni środki na wznowienie lub kontynuację produkcji. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 16)

W 2017 r. zakończyła się realizacja pierwszego Krajowego Planu Działania na rzecz ograniczenia ryzyka związanego ze stosowaniem środków ochrony roślin na lata 2013-2017. Kluczowym celem dla Polski w związku z realizacją ww. Krajowego Planu Działania było upowszechnianie ogólnych zasad integrowanej ochrony roślin oraz zapobieganie zagrożeniom związanym ze stosowaniem środków ochrony roślin. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 23)

available. These include financial guarantee schemes and insurance. (EC, 2017a, p.12)

The EU supports the competitiveness and sustainability of agriculture in Europe by financing a range of support measures (including direct payments) through the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). (EC, 2017b, p.11)

Nowoczesne ubezpieczenia rolnicze (MRiRW, 2018, p. 11)

Konieczne będzie przygotowanie polskich producentów do nadchodzących zmian, przede wszystkim przez aktywne działania informacyjne. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 17)

Opracowanie, przyjęcie i realizacja krajowego planu działania na rzecz ograniczenia ryzyka związanego ze stosowaniem środków ochrony roślin na lata 2018-2022 (MRiRW, 2018, p. 23)

wdrożenie zasad integrowanej ochrony roślin, w szczególności poprzez promowanie niechemicznych metod ochrony roślin, pozwoli na zmniejszenie zależności produkcji roślinnej od chemicznych środków ochrony roślin, co w efekcie pozwoli ograniczyć ryzyko związane z ich użyciem. Realizacja planu zapewni zatem bezpieczeństwo konsumentów produktów rolnych oraz poprawi jakość życia na terenach rolniczych, na których użycie tych preparatów jest najwyższe (MRiRW, 2018, p. 23)

Czynnikiem ograniczającym opłacalność produkcji roślinnej może być pojawienie się nowych, dotychczas niewystępujących na terenie Polski, organizmów szkodliwych dla roślin – sprawców chorób oraz szkodników. Organizmy takie mogą w sposób bezpośredni powodować straty w uprawach lub w sposób pośredni ograniczać opłacalność produkcji poprzez wzrost kosztów związanych z ochroną roślin.

prowadzone będą działania informacyjne i doradcze dla rolników, których efektem będzie opracowanie i wdrożenie rozwiązań stymulujących zmianę praktyk rolniczych mających na celu zwiększenie areału gleb, które poddawane są zabiegowi wapnowania w oparciu o analizy próbek gleb i precyzyjne zalecenia nawozowe. Jednym z nich będzie uruchomienie programu finansowania zabiegów wapniowania gleb. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 28)

Wystąpienie nowych organizmów szkodliwych może także stanowić barierę w eksporcie towarów pochodzenia roślinnego. Powyższe zagrożenia ograniczają przepisy fitosanitarne, określające zasady importu towarów pochodzenia roślinnego z państw trzecich, jak również zasady zwalczania i zapobiegania rozprzestrzenianiu się organizmów kwarantannowych (organizmów szczególnie groźnych i podlegających obowiązkowi zwalczania) (MRiRW, 2018, p. 24)

Zakwaszenie gleb stanowi dzisiaj jeden z najważniejszych elementów chemicznej degradacji gleb w Polsce. Szacuje się, że ok. 50% użytków rolnych wymaga uregulowania odczynu. Wapnowanie jest szczególnie istotne w kontekście wymogów środowiskowych i obowiązującej dyrektywy azotanowej obligującej do podejmowania działań na rzecz ograniczenia odpływu biogenów do wód. Jednocześnie,

Adaptability		wapnowanie korzystnie wpływa na wysokość i jakość płodów rolnych. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 28) WSPIERANIE PSZCZELARSTWA I RYNKU PRODUKTÓW PSZCZELICH (MRiRW, 2018, p. 29)	
	1. Middle-long term	Encouraging new entrants to take up farming is vital for the future of agriculture and rural communities, especially as the EU farming population is ageing. (EC, 2017b, p.9)	In order to encourage generational renewal, the Basic Payment awarded to new entrant Young Farmers (no more than 40 years of age) should be topped up by an additional payment available for a period of maximum 5 years (linked to the first installation). This shall be funded by up to 2% of the national envelope and will be compulsory for all Member states. (EC, 2013a, p.2) In addition to the Basic Payment Scheme/SAPS, each holding will receive a payment per hectare declared for the purpose of the basic payment for respecting certain agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment. Member States

will use 30% of their national envelope in order to pay for this. This is compulsory and failure to respect the Greening requirements will result in reductions and penalties which might in some cases go beyond the Greening payment. In years 1 & 2 the penalty for greening may not exceed 0%, 20% in the third year and as of the fourth the maximum penalty applied will be 25%. Of course, the green payment will only be granted for those areas that comply with the conditions (i.e. being eligible for BPS or SAPS, respect of greening obligations). (EC, 2013a, p.3)

the young farmer payment (YFP) – a top-up payment added to the basic payment – is obligatory in every member state. It is granted for a maximum of five years from the moment a young farmer takes over as the head of a farm holding. (EC, 2017b, p.9)

Rural development programmes, meanwhile, finance individual projects on farms and/or

		<p>other activities in rural areas on the basis of economic, environmental or territorial priorities. Funded through the EAFRD, this covers projects such as on-farm investment and modernisation, installation grants for young farmers, agri-environment measures, organic conversion, agri-tourism, village renewal or providing broadband internet coverage in rural areas. Accounting for almost 25% of CAP funding, these measures are generally co-financed by national, regional or private funds and generally extend over several years. (EC, 2017b, p.11)</p>
<p>2. Flexibility</p>	<p>Member states or regions will continue to design their own multi-annual programmes on the basis of the menu of measures available at EU level – in response to the needs of their own rural areas. (EC, 2013a, p.6)</p> <p>The new rules for the 2nd Pillar provide a more flexible approach than at present.</p>	<p>Member States will have the possibility of transferring up to 15% of their national envelope for Direct Payments (1st Pillar) to their Rural Development envelope. These amounts will not need to be co-funded. (EC, 2013a, p.4)</p> <p>Greening Equivalency: In order to avoid penalising those that already address</p>

Measures will no longer be classified at EU level into "axes" with associated minimum spending requirements per axis. Instead, it will be up to Member States / regions to decide which measures they use (and how) in order to achieve targets set against six broad "priorities" and their more detailed "focus areas" (sub-priorities), on the basis of sound analysis. The six priorities will cover: Fostering knowledge transfer and innovation; Enhancing competitiveness of all types of agriculture and the sustainable management of forests; Promoting food chain organisation, including processing and marketing, & risk management; Restoring, preserving & enhancing ecosystems; Promoting resource efficiency & the transition to a low-carbon economy; and Promoting social inclusion, poverty reduction and economic development in rural areas. (EC, 2013a, p.6)

environmental and sustainability issues, the accord foresees a "Greening equivalency" system whereby the application of environmentally beneficial practices already in place are considered to replace these basic requirements. (EC, 2013a, p.4)

The new rules for the 2nd Pillar provide a more flexible approach than at present. Measures will no longer be classified at EU level into "axes" with associated minimum spending requirements per axis. Instead, it will be up to Member States / regions to decide which measures they use (and how) in order to achieve targets set against six broad "priorities" and their more detailed "focus areas" (sub-priorities), on the basis of sound analysis. The six priorities will cover: Fostering knowledge transfer and innovation; Enhancing competitiveness of all types of agriculture and the sustainable management of forests; Promoting food chain organisation, including processing and marketing, & risk

management; Restoring, preserving & enhancing ecosystems; Promoting resource efficiency & the transition to a low-carbon economy; and Promoting social inclusion, poverty reduction and economic development in rural areas. (EC, 2013a, p.6)

Agri-environment - climate payments: Joint contracts, link to adequate training/information, greater flexibility when extending initial contracts (EC, 2013a, p.7)

the amount for pillar 1 was cut by 1.8% and for pillar 2 by 7.6% (in 2011 prices). (EC, 2013b, p.3)

the share of expenditure between pillars may change in 2014-2020, with the possibility to transfer up to 15% of their national envelopes between pillars, enabling Member States to better target spending to their specific priorities (EC, 2013b, p.4)

From 2014 onwards, the allocation of direct payments dedicated to coupled support, young farmers, small farmers, etc. will depend upon the choices made by Member States (EC, 2013b, p.4)

This flexibility will however be framed by well-defined regulatory and budgetary limits in order to ensure a level-playing field at European level and that common objectives are met. (EC, 2013b, p.5)

The flexibility offered to Member States to implement the new direct payments means that the share of funding allocated to different schemes can potentially vary significantly throughout the EU. (EC, 2013b, p.7)

Member States will have to build their RDP's based upon at least four of the six common EU priorities (EC, 2013b, p.9)

Compared to the previous programming periods, there is increased flexibility in the use

and combination of measures (20 in total) to better address specific territorial needs (Kantor Management Consultants, 2015, p. 5)

Member States have the possibility to make changes in their implementing decisions (Ecorys et. al., 2016, p.8)

Whilst Member States compose their programmes from the same list of measures, they have the flexibility to address the issues of most concern within their respective territory reflecting their specific economic, natural and structural conditions. As an integral part of rural development programmes, the 'Leader approach' encourages local people to address local issues. (EC, 2017a, p.7)

national authorities are responsible for the administration and control of direct payments to farmers in their country. Each country also has a certain level of flexibility in the way they grant these payments to take account of national farming conditions, which vary

greatly throughout the European Union. (EC, 2017b, p.1)

As from 2015, active farmers in the EU have access to compulsory schemes applicable in all EU countries, as well as to voluntary schemes if established at the national level. (EC, 2017b, p.2)

Generally, direct payments are not granted to a farmer if the total amount due and/or the area of land eligible for payment is too small. The exact threshold varies from country to country as it is set by national administrations, but it is generally between €100 and €500 and/or 0.3 ha to 5 ha respectively. (EC, 2017b, p.5)

Farmers are obliged to maintain their land in good agricultural and environmental condition. This means, among others things, protecting the soil against erosion, maintaining soil organic matter and soil structure, avoiding the deterioration of habitats, water

management and safeguarding landscape features. The exact standards that farmers must meet in these cases are set at the national, not EU, level. (EC, 2017b, p.5)

EU member states (MS) can combine different direct payment schemes to ensure efficient support to farmers, adapted to their national context. Some are compulsory and some are optional. (EC, 2017b, p.5)

Depending on the choices made by each national authority, the basic payment accounts for between 12% and 68% of their national budget allocation. (EC, 2017b, p.7)

The basic payment is applied either as the basic payment scheme (BPS) or as a transitional simplified scheme, the single area payment scheme (SAPS). (EC, 2017b, p.7)

All entitlements allocated to a farmer have the same value, but differences in the value of

entitlements may exist between farmers, if a member state opted for such an approach. (EC, 2017b, p.7)

Member states must allocate 30% of their direct payment allocation to this greening payment. (EC, 2017b, p.8)

A ratio of permanent grassland to agricultural land is set by member states at national or regional level (with a 5% margin of flexibility). (EC, 2017b, p.8)

Farmers with arable land exceeding 15 ha must ensure that at least 5% of their land is an ecological focus area with a view to safeguarding and improving biodiversity on farms. (EC, 2017b, p.8)

Member states may allow farmers to meet one or more greening requirements through equivalent (alternative) practices. (EC, 2017b, p.8)

The share of direct payments that member states can dedicate to voluntary coupled support is generally limited to 8%, although certain exceptions are allowed (EC, 2017b, p.9)

The YFP can account for up to 2% of total direct payment national allocations. (EC, 2017b, p.9)

Areas with natural constraints (ANCs) are areas where farming is handicapped by natural or other specific constraints. The areas are set by member states on the basis of biophysical criteria (such as slopes for example). (EC, 2017b, p.10)

W ramach PROW 2014-2020 realizowanych jest 14 działań i 30 poddziałań, których celem jest wsparcie rozwoju sektora rolno-spożywczego i obszarów wiejskich. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 17)

	<p>3. Variety and tailor-made responses</p>	<p>In the new period, Member States / regions will also have the possibility to design thematic sub-programmes to pay especially detailed attention to issues such as young farmers, small farms, mountain areas, women in rural areas, climate change mitigation / adaptation, biodiversity and short supply chains. Higher support rates will be available within sub-programmes in some cases. (EC, 2013a, p.6)</p> <p>There is new flexibility for Member States in the budgeting and implementation of first Pillar instruments, acknowledging the wide diversity of agriculture, agronomic production potential and climatic, environmental as well as socio-economic conditions and needs across the EU. (EC, 2013b, p.5)</p> <p>Given the pressure on natural resources, agriculture has to improve its environmental performance through more sustainable production methods. Farmers also have</p>	<p>There will also be Rural Development funding for advice to small farmers for economic development and restructuring grants for regions with many such small farms. (EC, 2013a, p.3)</p> <p>Non-agricultural activities: Grants for start-up and development of micro- and small businesses (EC, 2013a, p.7)</p> <p>Other instruments under the second pillar which enhance competitiveness at farm level include restructuring and modernisation measures as well as start-up aid for young farmers. Furthermore, there is a focus on bridging the gap between science and practice via the Farm Advisory System, as well as training and innovation 8 programmes. These instruments are aimed at helping the farm sector to adapt to new trends and technologies, thus becoming more resource efficient, cost effective and capable of</p>
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to adapt to challenges stemming from changes to the climate by pursuing climate change mitigation and adaptation actions (e.g. by developing greater resilience to disasters such as flooding, drought and fire). (EC, 2013b, p.6)

As regards Poland's rural area the ESIF will contribute to increasing the competitiveness of the Polish agriculture, the sustainable management of natural resources and climate action in rural areas as well as their balanced territorial development. (EC, 2014, p.2)

To avoid negative side effects of some farming practices, the EU provides incentives to farmers to work in a sustainable and environmentally friendly manner. (EC, 2017a, p.4)

Up to 5% of the national allocation for direct payments can be used for top-up payments to farmers in these ANC areas – an option applied at present only by Denmark as from

adapting to emerging challenges. (EC, 2013b, p.6)

at least 30% of the budget of each Rural Development programme must be reserved for voluntary measures that are beneficial for the environment and climate change. These include agri–environmental climate measures, organic farming, Areas of Natural Constraints (ANC), Natura 2000 areas, forestry measures and investments which are beneficial for the environment or climate. (EC, 2013b, p.7)

The Member States' implementation choices with respect to viable food production have been assessed as being in general more tailored to local needs than in the previous CAP. For agricultural income this was more apparent than for agricultural productivity. (Ecorys et. al., 2016, p. 6)

National (sometimes regional) programmes of development are established to address the

2015, and Slovenia as from 2017. Support for farmers in these areas is also possible – and mainly provided - through the rural development programmes. (EC, 2017b, p.10)

Rural development programmes, meanwhile, finance individual projects on farms and/or other activities in rural areas on the basis of economic, environmental or territorial priorities. Funded through the EAFRD, this covers projects such as on-farm investment and modernisation, installation grants for young farmers, agri-environment measures, organic conversion, agri-tourism, village renewal or providing broadband internet coverage in rural areas. Accounting for almost 25% of CAP funding, these measures are generally co-financed by national, regional or private funds and generally extend over several years. (EC, 2017b, p.11)

the common agricultural policy is not just about making sure Europe can feed itself.

specific needs and challenges facing rural areas. (EC, 2017a, p.7)

Support to young farmers is also provided under the EU's rural development programmes, in the form of a start-up aid. (EC, 2017b, p.9)

	<p>It also contributes to some of the other key objectives of the European Union: boosting jobs and growth in the food and farming sector, tackling sustainability and climate change and delivering wider benefits for society. (EC, 2017b, p.12)</p>	
<p>4. Social learning</p>	<p>Innovation: This key theme (and more specifically the planned European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity & Sustainability – the "EIP") will be served by various rural development measures such as "knowledge transfer", "cooperation" and "investments in physical assets". The EIP will promote resource efficiency, productivity and the low-emission and climate-friendly/-resilient development of agriculture and forestry. This should be achieved, inter alia, through greater cooperation between agriculture and research in order to accelerate technological transfer to farmers (EC, 2013a, p.7)</p>	<p>The maximum EU co-funding rates will be up to 85% in less developed regions, the outermost regions and the smaller Aegean islands, 75% in transition regions, 63% in other transition regions and 53% in other regions for most payments, but can be higher for the measures supporting knowledge transfer, cooperation, the establishment of producer groups and organisations and young farmer installation grants, as well as for LEADER projects and for spending related to the environment and climate change under various measures. (EC, 2013a, p.6)</p>

Knowledge – “a knowledge-based agriculture”: Strengthened measures for Farm Advisory Services (also linked to climate change mitigation and adaptation, to environmental challenges and to economic development and training) (EC, 2013a, p.7)

Producer groups / organisations: Support for setting up groups / organisations on the basis of a business plan and limited to entities defined as SMEs (EC, 2013a, p.7)

Co-operation: Expanded possibilities to support technological, environmental and commercial cooperation (e.g. pilot projects, joint environmental schemes, development of short supply chains and local markets) (EC, 2013a, p.7)

In the future, our farmers will have to produce more with less. This could be achieved through the development of instruments, such as innovation partnerships, to promote innovation in agriculture by bridging the

LEADER: Greater emphasis on awareness-raising and other preparatory support for strategies; promoting flexibility for operating with other funds in local areas, i.e. rural-urban co-operation; N.B. LEADER will now be used as the common approach for community-led local development by the following ESI Funds: the ERDF, ESF, EMFF and EAFRD. (EC, 2013a, p.7)

This whole set of complementary policy instruments is accompanied by related training measures and other support from the Farm Advisory System, insights gained from the Innovation Partnership and applied research, which should help farmers to implement appropriate solutions for their specific situations. (EC, 2013b, p.7)

High quality in the provision of knowledge transfer and advisory services is ensured through entry requirements for the supported

existing gap between research and farming practice and facilitating communication and cooperation among stakeholders (farmers, advisers, agro-business, scientists, administrations and others). (EC, 2017a, p.11)

Podjęmowane działania nakierowane na wzmocnienie współpracy zmierzać będą do: - wspierania oddolnych form integracji producentów rolnych, polegających na tworzeniu i rozwoju spółdzielni, grup producentów rolnych i organizacji producentów, związków grup producentów rolnych i zrzeszeń organizacji producentów oraz organizacji międzybranżowych, - wzmocnienia współpracy w łańcuchu dostaw żywności, w tym zwalczania nieuczciwych praktyk handlowych, - zapewnienia dzielenia się wiedzą i środkami produkcji w ramach świadczenia wspólnych usług. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 13)

organisations (Kantor Management Consultants, 2015, p. 8)

Spółdzielnie rolników (MRiRW, 2018, p. 11)

Ponadto, przygotowany został projekt badania naukowego w zakresie możliwości rozwoju ubezpieczeń gospodarczych w rolnictwie. Projekt bazuje na solidnie ugruntowanej najnowszej podbudowie teoretycznej i empirycznej, a więc na zachowaniach rolników w warunkach występowania wielu ryzyk, asymetrii informacji i niekompletności kontraktów ubezpieczeniowych, z drugiej natomiast strony integruje kwestie makroekonomiczne (konsumpcja, oszczędności, inwestycje oraz wzrost) i odnoszące się do finansów publicznych z mikroekonomicznymi (konkurencyjność, regulacje rynków i pomnażanie wartości dodanej) z problematyką sektorową (funkcjonowanie rolnictwa w sposób zrównoważony, nastawionego na wdrażanie

Poza potencjałem gospodarczym, spółdzielczość rolników reprezentuje potencjał społeczny, demokratyczne zasady postępowania wewnątrzspółdzielczego oraz przedkładanie potrzeb członków nad maksymalizację zysku. Spółdzielczość, jako forma zbiorowej zaradności lokalnych społeczności, stwarza realne szanse na aktywność gospodarczą i społeczną przez budowanie spójności i integralności społecznej obszarów wiejskich. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 40)

Samorząd rolniczy ma do spełnienia ważną rolę, jako organizacja mająca wpływ na rozwiązywanie problemów rolnictwa i reprezentująca interesy zrzeszonych w nim rolników. Izby rolnicze są i powinny być najważniejszą organizacją samorządu rolniczego na obszarach wiejskich. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 40)

innowacji, niedoinwestowanego w części sfer działalności, dotykanego przez tzw. przesunięcia ryzyk, itp., oraz konfrontowanego ze zmianami klimatu). Efektem projektu będzie przygotowanie propozycji rozwiązań w zakresie ubezpieczeń i innych instrumentów przewidzianych w regulacjach unijnych (Fundusze Wsparcia Wzajemnego) lub realizowanych na świecie (np. ubezpieczenia indeksowe przychodów). Rozwiązania te będą zawierały ocenę zarówno z popytowego jak i podażowego punktu widzenia (szacunkowe kalkulacje składki netto za poszczególne rozwiązania). (MRiRW, 2018, p. 16)

Wsparcie sektora rolnictwa ekologicznego realizowane jest przez wsparcie producentów rolnych w ramach działań Programu Rozwoju Obszarów Wiejskich na lata 2014-2020 (PROW 2014-2020), jak i rozwój nauki służącej rolnictwu ekologicznemu (MRiRW, 2018, p. 16)

w ramach przewidzianego w SOR projekcie pn. Energetyka rozproszona, w realizacji którego współuczestniczy MRiRW, planowane jest przygotowanie działań edukacyjnych prowadzonych m.in. przez ośrodki doradztwa rolniczego w zakresie zastosowania odnawialnych źródeł energii z wykorzystaniem form organizacyjnych preferowanych w ramach nowych uregulowań prawnych – energetyka w formule prosumenckiej, spółdzielnie energetyczne na obszarach wiejskich. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 31)

W ramach KOWR zostanie utworzona jednostka/platforma pn. Akademia Producenta i Eksportera (APE), do której zadań należeć będzie m.in.: - gromadzenie i upowszechnianie wśród importerów informacji i materiałów informacyjnopromocyjnych na temat krajowego rynku rolno-spożywczego i jego ofercie eksportowej, - gromadzenie i upowszechnianie wśród krajowych

producentów i eksporterów informacji i materiałów informacyjno-promocyjnych na temat zagranicznych rynków zbytu produktów rolnospożywczych i ich zapotrzebowaniu, - gromadzenie i upowszechnianie informacji na temat uwarunkowań instytucjonalnoorganizacyjnych w Polsce i sprzedaży krajowych produktów na rynkach UE i państw trzecich, - stymulowanie rozwoju i promowanie handlu na rynkach zorganizowanych, - upowszechnianie wiedzy dotyczącej propagowania innowacyjności produktowych, organizacyjnych i marketingowych we współpracy z ośrodkami naukowymi i jednostkami doradztwa rolniczego, - propagowanie rozwiązań z zakresu gospodarki o obiegu zamkniętym, w tym zapobieganie marnotrawieniu żywności, na obszarach wiejskich, - upowszechnianie wśród uczestników wiedzy na temat przeciwdziałania marnowaniu żywności.

W ramach APE organizowane będą między innymi cykliczne szkolenia i seminaria oraz spotkania przedstawicieli i interesariuszy celem pogłębienia współpracy i transferu wiedzy (MRiRW, 2018, p. 39)

W 2018 r. wzmacniane będą procesy i mechanizmy transferu wiedzy i innowacji z nauki do praktyki rolniczej, w szczególności w ramach Sieci na rzecz innowacji w rolnictwie i na obszarach wiejskich. Po stronie sektora badań i rozwoju w proces ten zostaną zaangażowane przede wszystkim instytuty naukowe i państwowe jednostki doradztwa rolniczego. Partnerem w procesie są m.in. grupy operacyjne na rzecz innowacji oraz rolnicy, przedsiębiorstwa rolno-spożywcze i inne podmioty zainteresowane wdrażaniem innowacji. Kontynuowane będą działania na rzecz zacieśnienia współpracy z Narodowym Centrum Badań i Rozwoju oraz silniejszego włączenia instytutów badawczych w program Horyzont 2020. Ponadto w 2018 r.

kontynuowane będą działania mające na celu zapewnienie stabilnego finansowania działalności badawczo-rozwojowej instytutów badawczych oraz zwiększenie efektywności w zakresie opracowania i wdrażania innowacji, w tym działania na rzecz powołania Sieci Instytutów Badawczych w obszarze nauk rolniczych oraz Rady Badań Rolniczych i Innowacji. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 44)

Prowadzone będą działania na rzecz podnoszenia jakości usług świadczonych przez państwowe jednostki doradztwa rolniczego oraz podnoszenia jakości kapitału ludzkiego w tych jednostkach, w szczególności poprzez zapewnienie odpowiednich szkoleń oraz warunków pracy i płacy doradców. Jednocześnie podejmowane będą działania na rzecz poprawy bazy dydaktyczno-lokalowej i szerszego wykorzystania technik

			<p>informatycznych w pracy doradczej. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 45)</p> <p>podejmowane będą działania na rzecz wzmocnienia doradztwa technologicznego. (MRiRW, 2018, p. 46)</p>
Transformability	1. Long term	<p>three long-term CAP objectives: viable food production, sustainable management of natural resources and climate action and balanced territorial development. (EC, 2013b, p.2)</p> <p>EU agriculture needs to attain higher levels of production of safe and quality food, while preserving the natural resources that agricultural productivity depends upon. (EC, 2013b, p.3)</p> <p>In taking these key decisions Member States have a responsibility to make the most of the opportunities offered by the reform to set out future strategies for their agricultural sectors that will ensure their competitiveness and</p>	<p>As in the past, it will be implemented through national and/or regional rural development programmes (RDP's) which, for a seven-year period, set out the actions to be undertaken and the corresponding allocation of funding for these measures. (EC, 2013b, p.9)</p> <p>Member States did not document a joined up, coherent strategy on which to base their choices about the implementation of the CAP (Ecorys et al., 2016, p. 9).</p>

sustainability over the long-term. (EC, 2013b, p.10)

There is little evidence to support that Pillar 1 implementation decisions have been based on carefully designed strategies that incorporate long-term objectives and integration with Pillar 2 measures (Ecorys et al., 2016, p. 6).

During the period 2014-2020 the policy is expected to provide improved internet services and infrastructure to 18 million rural citizens — the equivalent of 6.4 % of the EU's rural population (EC, 2017a, p.4)

In the coming decade our farmers will become more efficient and more competitive. (EC, 2017a, p.11)

Between 2014 and 2020 the EU plans to make available to farmers almost 4 million places on training courses and 1.4 million advisory sessions with a focus on economic

		and environmental performance of farms. About 335 000 farmers can expect to receive investment support to restructure and modernise their farms and 175 000 young farmers will receive support to launch their businesses. (EC, 2017a, p.12)	
	2. Dismantling incentives that support the status quo	The key characteristics of the architecture of the EU Rural development policy remain untouched by the reform. (EC, 2013b, p.9)	In 1992 market management represented over 90% of total CAP expenditure, driven by export refunds and intervention purchases. By the end of 2013 it dropped to just 5% (EC, 2013b, p.4)
	3. In-depth learning		
	4. Enhancing and accelerating niche innovations	The new rules for the 2 nd Pillar provide a more flexible approach than at present. Measures will no longer be classified at EU level into "axes" with associated minimum spending requirements per axis. Instead, it will be up to Member States / regions to decide which measures they use (and how) in order to achieve targets set against six	

broad "priorities" and their more detailed "focus areas" (sub-priorities), on the basis of sound analysis. The six priorities will cover: Fostering knowledge transfer and innovation; Enhancing competitiveness of all types of agriculture and the sustainable management of forests; Promoting food chain organisation, including processing and marketing, & risk management; Restoring, preserving & enhancing ecosystems; Promoting resource efficiency & the transition to a low-carbon economy; and Promoting social inclusion, poverty reduction and economic development in rural areas. (EC, 2013b, p.6)